

PLANNING COMPETENCE AND STAFF PERFORMANCE IN MUNI UNIVERSITY, UGANDA

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between planning competences and staff performance in the unique context of Muni University. In the study, a descriptive cross-sectional survey design was used with a sample size of 109. Purposive, stratified and systematic sampling techniques were used to select respondents. Data was analyzed through frequencies and percentages, Spearman rank order correlation, coefficient of determination, and regression. There was a relationship between the dependent and independent variable.

Keywords: planning competences, staff performance

1. Introduction

The study examined the relationship between management competences and staff performance in Muni University. In this study, planning competences was conceived as the independent variable and performance was the dependent variable. It is worth noting that management competences have many dimensions which include task skills, contingency management skills and job role/environment skills (Allen, 2012).

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1.1 Background to the study

Over the past two to three decades, universities world over have faced major challenges in terms of their management and staff performance. These challenges have resulted in significant transformations in the scope of their mission, governance, knowledge production and circulation, and relations with wider national, regional and global economies and societies (Barnett, 2009). These transformations are part of a wider 'paradigmatic transition' facing all societies and universities, around the world (Santos, 2010: 1). Whilst at present what might be the enduring features of this transition are unknown, some of its constituent elements, and management politics, are visible, and are cause for major concern.

In Africa, in essence these management politics are changing what it means to talk about the university, critical knowledge production and performance in general. An underlying thread in all of these challenges is the dominance of management theories and performance of university staff.

Today, academics and University staff, their Universities, cities, regions and nations, are measured, compared, rated, ranked, rejected, targeted for treatment, re-measured in an intense process of staff performance, scrutiny and identity making. In other words, the competitive comparative advantage has been to think in imaginative ways as to how to become a world class education hub by buying in world class brands, world class academics and competent staff.

Management competences and staff performance is better understood in the context of this study with the use of Competence-based Strategic Management theory. Competence-based Strategic Management theory is a way of thinking about how organizations gain high performance for a significant period of time (Katz, 2013).

The theory further explains how organizations can develop [sustainable competitive advantage](#) in a systematic and structural way (Baggozi & Edwards, 1998). It is an integrative [strategy theory](#) that incorporates economic, organizational and behavioural concerns in a framework that is dynamic, systemic, cognitive and holistic (Sanchez and Heene, 2004). Competence-based Strategic Management theory defines competence as: the ability to sustain the coordinated deployment of [resources](#) in ways that helps an [organization](#) achieve its [goals](#) while creating and distributing value to customers and stakeholders (Draft & Lengel, 2008).

Another theory that was adopted to underpin this study is the institutional theory. This theory takes a sociological perspective to explain organizational structures and behavior (Dunn, 2010:4). Staff performance at university is a function that is heavily structure-managed and the behavior of individuals who manage the process through various structures has a significant role in improving the staff performance of organizations through applying the principles to make appropriate decisions. The

institutional theory draws attention to how organization decision making is influenced by the social and cultural factors as identified by Scott, (2001:32), and in particular how rationalized activities are adopted by organizations. The theory emphasizes the use of rules, laws and sanctions as enforcement mechanism, with expedience as basis for compliance (Scott 2004:23). And by its nature, university management and performance is a rules-bound game. When applied, the theory helps to explain the staff's effect of institutional decision making and the influence of the regulatory and oversight department in influencing performance (Scott, 2001).

Conceptually, this study was guided by the concepts of management competencies and staff performance as the independent and depend variables respectively. According to Leis (2011:12), management is the organization and coordination of the activities of a business in order to achieve defined objectives. Management consists of interlocking functions of creating corporate policy and organizing, planning, controlling and directing an organization's resources in order to achieve the organizational goals and objectives. In this study, management was measured in terms of planning, budgeting and communicating.

Staff Performance is accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. In management, staff performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract. Staff Performance has been described as "*the degree of achievement of certain effort or undertaking*". It relates to the prescribed goals or objectives which form the parameters (Chitkara, 2005).

From management perspective, it is all about meeting or exceeding stakeholders' needs and expectations from a task. It invariably involves placing consideration on three major elements, i.e. time, cost and quality (Project management institute, 2004). For purposes of this study, staff performance will be measured in terms of time, cost and quality.

Competence models may be applicable to all employees in an organization or they may be position specific. Identifying employee competencies can contribute to improved staff performance. They are most effective if they meet several critical standards, including linkage to, and leverage within an organization's human resource system (Walumbwa, et. al. 2008). Core competencies differentiate an organization from its competition and create a company's competitive advantage in the marketplace.

An organizational [core competency](#) is its strategic strength (Ammons & Weare, 2009). To be competent a person would need to be able to interpret the situation in the context and to have a repertoire of possible actions to take and have trained in the possible actions in the repertoire, if this is relevant. Regardless of training, competency would grow through experience and the extent of an individual to learn and adapt.

Contextually, meaningful higher education systems require successful education institutions. Such institutions cannot succeed without competent management. Although this is true the world over, concept of competent university staff and how to achieve it differ (Walumbwa, et. al. 2008). These differences might arise from variations in culture and traditions, historic experiences or from levels of development, to name just a few reasons. Regardless of these differences, there is wide spread agreement that better staff performance can help higher education institutions achieve their goals, reduce costs and frictions and increase effectiveness (Ammons & Weare, 2009).

It is impossible to run a university like a private company; however, it is not only possible, but also necessary to transform the management tools developed in the private sector and apply them appropriately to management in higher education (Asree & Zain, 2010). Once the importance of management competences is recognized and accepted, there is a need to identify how the concept applies to the specific duties of those who manage universities, faculties, departments or schools. This can elucidate issues and skills pertinent to such management duties. And, it is important to clarify which persons in which positions at a university need to have which competencies (Assadifard, Roya et al 2011). And, if said competences and persons are identified, it still remains to establish the right means of providing those competences for better staff performance.

Management competences can distinguish and differentiate an organization from its competitors. While two organizations may be alike in financial results, the way in which the results were achieved could be different based on the competences that fit their particular strategy and organizational culture (Beheshtifar, 2011). By aligning competences to business strategies, organizations can better recruit and select employees for their organizations (Blair, 1999).

Competences have become a precise way for employers to distinguish superior from average or below average performance. The reason for this is because competencies extend beyond measuring baseline characteristics and or skills used to define and assess job performance (Brinckmann, 2008). In addition to recruitment and selection, a well sound Competency Model will help with performance management, succession planning and career development.

Competences are also what people need to be successful in their jobs. Job competencies are not the same as job task (Burnett & Dutsch, 2006). Competences include all the related knowledge, skills, abilities, and attributes that form a person's job. This set of context-specific qualities is correlated with superior job performance and can be used as a standard against which to measure job performance as well as to develop, recruit, and hire employees.

Lastly, competences can provide a structured model that can be used to integrate management practices throughout the organization. Competencies that align their recruiting, performance management, training and development and reward practices to reinforce key behaviors that the organization values. Competency models can help organizations align their initiatives to their overall business strategy (Bennis, 1984).

2. Statement of the problem

In a bid to improve equitable access to university education, the government of Uganda has spent many resources in Universities including Muni University with the aim that the resources will be managed competently to bring about better performance (Khan, 2015). Despite the heavy investment in terms of resources, the staff at these Universities has not performed to the expected standards and this is evidenced in the many strikes by staff and students. The performance of the universities is less than expected as shown by 64% of the set target still off track (Uganda Government Annual Performance Report, 2015).

Consequently, the declining staff performance has been a source of rising concerns over lack of achievement of planned targets in time. In the circumstances, one would wonder whether the staff have had the require competences to perform the tasks. Therefore, this study investigated the relationship between management competences and staff performance in Muni University.

3. Methodology

This study used a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design. In a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design, the study variables, that is, independent and dependent variables were measured at the same point in time and this enabled description as well as comparison of various factors associated with the study (Bhattacharjee, 2012). This further helped the researcher to ensure that people's views and opinions were sought and described accordingly to establish how management competencies affect performance within the study scope.

The study used a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design because the study intended to pick only representative sample elements of the cross section of the study population. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches.

3.1 Study population

The study was done at Muni University. The actual population is the 15 University Council members, 63 Academic staff, 81 Administrative staff, 15 support staff and 23

guild officials. The study targeted key players in the running of Muni University who are conversant with the management affairs of the University.

3.2 Determination of sample size

Sampling is the procedure a researcher uses to gather people, places or things to study. It was the process of selecting a number of individuals or objects from the population such that the selected group contains elements representative of the characteristics found in the entire group (Orodho & Kombo, 2002). A sample size of 112 respondents was determined using statistical tables of Krejcie & Morgan as cited by Amin (2005). The sample included various categories as specified in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Research respondents by category and sample

No.	Category of respondents	(N)	(S)	Sampling technique
1	Academic staff	63	14	Simple random sampling
2	Administrative staff	81	62= 34 (permanent basis 28 (contract basis)	Stratified sampling
3	Support staff	25	14	Simple random sampling
4	University Council	15	6	Purposive sampling
5	University guild	15	10	Simple random sampling
6	Total	214	112	

Key: *N* – Population Size, *S* – Recommended Sample Population (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

The sample sizes in the Table 1 above are derived from Krejcie & Morgan (1970) table given in Appendix.

3.3 Sampling techniques and procedure

Purposive sampling was used to select University Council members who were interviewed. The researcher chose this technique to select this category of respondents in order to focus on those that are the most knowledgeable and with vast experience about what was to be investigated.

Simple random sampling was used to select Academic staff and the student guild expected to participate in the research. The researcher chose this sampling technique for this particular group because this group of respondents is homogenous

with almost equal understanding of the topic under investigation. In addition, they constitute a reasonable number to support selection by this procedure.

Stratified sampling was used to select Administrative staff because it will enable the researcher to determine desired levels of sampling of representation for each group, and provide administrative efficiency.

3.4 Data collection methods

This includes the specific techniques to be used in the collection of data (UTAMU Guideline, 2041). There are several methods to collect required data for research purpose and these include face-to-face interview, key informants interview, focus group discussion (FGD), survey, observation, and documentary review. However, for the purpose of this study focus was on survey and documentary review and face to face interviews.

3.5 Survey

The selection of the survey method was guided by the nature of data to be collected, the time available and the objectives of the study (Touliatos and Compton, 1988). This method was used on all respondents who were selected to participate in this study. One of the reasons why this method was preferred is because the study involved variables that cannot not be observed and can only be derived from respondents' views, opinions and feelings (Touliatos & Compton, 1988).

3.6 Documentary review

Document analysis was used in studying the already existing literature and documents in order to either find gaps that could be filled by the study or evidence that could support or contradict the quantitative and quantitative findings (Kothari, 2004). To exhaustively investigate the study, the researcher used triangulation to capture a variety of information, and reveal discrepancies that a single technique might not reveal (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003).

3.7 Data collection instruments

The researcher was guided by the nature of the problem under investigation in as far as data collection instruments are concerned. Accordingly, the study used interview guide, questionnaire, focused group discussion topics and documentary checklists.

3.8 Validity and reliability of instruments

As observed by Vogt (2007), a number of studies have used this instrument and found both their reliability and validity values to be acceptable to the population being

studied and in a different context thus recommends for testing the validity and reliability of the instruments. The instruments were pre-tested to determine their validity and reliability.

3.9 Validity of instruments

Vogt (2007) defines validity as —the truth or accuracy of the research (pp. 117). Saunders et al (2009) adds that it is the extent to which the data collection instrument measures as well as the appropriateness of the measures coming to accurate conclusions. Validity tests was conducted for content, criterion & construct validity test how well the instrument is representative, captures relationships between the variables as well as measures the concepts (Saunders et al, 2009); Vogt, 2007; and Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

This study utilized triangulation to ensure validity of research findings prior to the administration of the research instruments. The instruments were checked by experts including the supervisors of the researcher. Content validity ratio was used to calculate the Content Validity Index, using formula below;

$$CVI = \frac{\text{Total Number of items rated by all respondents}}{\text{Total Number of items in the Instrument}}$$

A content validity index of 0.7 and above according to Amin, (2005) qualified the instrument for the study.

3.10 Reliability of instruments

Reliability is defined by Vogt (2007) as the consistency of either measurement or design to give the same conclusions if used as different times or by different scholars. The first step in ensuring reliability is by providing clear operational definitions of the variables under study. Thereafter, internal consistency was measured through internal consistency reliability (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010) using split-half reliability method.

3.11 Data Analysis

The findings of the study were analyzed using quantitative method. This involved uncovering structures, extracting important variables, detecting any irregularity and testing any assumptions (Kombo & Tromp, 2006). The researcher further used triangulation method of analysis so as to come up with appropriate conclusions and recommendations.

4. Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Results

4.1 Response rate

A total of 109 questionnaires were administered, 107 were returned and 4 could not be used and were therefore excluded, leaving a total of 103 questionnaires for considerations. For the case of interviews, out of 11 targeted respondents six were interviewed. These included the Vice Chancellor, Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academic Affairs), University Secretary, University Librarian and two members of the Governing Council. Managers were interviewed to solicit detailed information about different management competences and their effect on staff performance at Muni University.

The table below gives the detailed information of the study response rate.

Table 4.2.1 Response rate

Instrument	Target population	Actual response	Response rate
Questionnaire	109	103	94.5%
Interview guide	11	06	55.5%

Source: Primary data, 2017

As indicated in Table 4.2.1, 109 questionnaires were administered and 103 were returned, giving a response rate of 94.5%. Similarly, Table 4.2.1 shows that 11 interviewees were targeted and 06 were reached, giving a response rate of 55.5%, this is in line with the expected threshold of 50% for quality data according to Amin (2005).

4.2 Characteristics of the respondents

This section contains a detailed description of the results about gender, age, level of education and experience of respondent obtained after data analysis. In this section, frequency tables were used to represent findings against interpretation of demographic characteristics of respondents. The information was sought because the nature of the study necessitated the gathering of opinions and findings from across section of different people for a wider perspective and analysis of the findings.

Table 4.3.1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Gender	Male	81	79	79
	Female	22	21	100
Age	20-29	52	50	50
	30-39	39	38	88
	40-49	12	12	12
Level of education	O Level	4	4	4

	A Level	10	10	10	14
	Diploma	34	33	33	47
	Degree	52	50	50	97
	Masters	3	3	3	100
	PhD				
Experience	Above 6 years	12	12	12	12
	4 to 5 years	35	34	34	46
	2 to 3 years	24	23	23	69
	1 year and below	32	31	31	100

Source: Primary data, 2017

On gender, as is given in the Table 4.3.1, majority of the respondents in this study were male and were 81 constituting 79% of the sample. The female respondents were 22 (21%). In relation to the age distributions of respondents included in the study, the majority of the respondents, that is, 52 comprising 50% of the sample was between 20 to 29 years followed by those between 30 and 39 years (38%).

Cumulatively, the majority of the study respondents, 91 (88%) were within the age of 20 to 29 years. The study sample is not different in the characteristic presented from what one would find in the entire staff population of the selected case study.

With regard to the level of education among the people included in the study, half of the respondents were degree holders constituting 52 (50%) followed by diploma holders 34 (33%). A level respondents were 10 (10%), O level respondents were 10% and Masters holders were 3 representing 3%. Collectively, respondents in the study that had attained O level education, A level education and Masters Degrees were 17 (17%). The result of the table shows that majority of the study respondents were educated to Bachelor degree level as this was expected given that the study context is a University, where most positions require one to have a degree level of education. As indicated in the Table 4.3.1 above, the majority of the respondents 35 (34%) had worked for a period of between four and five years, followed by those who had worked for one year and below who were 32 (31%). 23% of the respondents of the study had served Muni University for a period of two to three years. Further as indicated in Table 4.3.1 above 12% of the respondents had experience working with the University for over six years. Those who had worked for 6 years and above were 12 (12%). This is majorly the case given that the University is relatively new. 3

4.3 Planning Competences and Staff Performance

The study examines the extent to which planning competence affects staff performance in Muni University. The staff at Muni University was requested to respond to the study

questionnaire by indicating their position using a five point Likert scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree as shown in the table below.

Table 4.4.1 Descriptive statistics of responses regarding the different dimensions of planning competences of staff in Muni University investigated in the study

Planning competences	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Plans are simple	42 (41%)	41 (40%)	5 (5%)	15 (14%)	0 (0%)
Plans are specific	38 (37%)	37 (36%)	7 (7%)	18 (17%)	3 (3%)
Plans are realistic	38 (37%)	43 (42%)	6 (6%)	12 (11%)	4 (4%)
Plans are complete	51 (49%)	34 (33%)	5 (5%)	11 (11%)	2 (2%)
Plans are practical	25 (24%)	53 (52%)	16 (16%)	9 (8%)	0 (0%)

Source: Primary data, 2017

The study findings in Table 4.4.1 above show that the majority of the respondents comprising 81% agreed that plans at Muni University were simple, with 41% strongly agreeing. Only 15 (14%) disagreed. Cumulatively, respondents who are in agreement with the view that planning at Muni University is simple comprise the majority, that is, 83 (81%) implying that at Muni University planning is made simple staff for the staff. In line with these findings, the majority of the respondents stated that plans are easy to understand and act on.

In relation to whether the plans at Muni University were specific or not, majority of the respondents to the study comprising 74% agreed that plans at Muni University were specific in terms of objectives of which 38 (37%) when asked whether plans were specific indicated that they strongly agree while 37 (36%) agreed. On the same, 7 (7%) were neutral while 18 (17%) of the respondents disagreed and 3 (3%) strongly disagreed. These findings generally point to the high competence of developing specific plan by Staff at Muni University.

Furthermore, in relation to the question of how realistic plans at Muni University are, Table 4.4.1 further indicated that majority of the respondents comprising 79% agreed that Muni university had realistic plans of which 38 (37%) when asked whether the University plan were realistic responded that they strongly agree while 43 (42%) agreed and 6 (6%) were undecided, 12 (11%) disagreed and 4 (4%) strongly disagreed.

It was further found out that completeness of plans implemented was good for the staff. Results showed that majority of the respondents comprising 84% agreed that the plans were complete of which 49 (51%) when asked whether the plans were complete responded that they strongly agree while 34 (33%) agree, 5 (5%) were undecided while 11 (11%) disagreed and 2 (2%) strongly disagreed. The finding shows

that Muni University offers complete plans for the staff and this is supported by the highest number of respondents 85 (82%) who are in agreement.

4.4 Correlation results of the relationship between planning competences and staff performance in Muni University

Having presented findings about planning competences and staff performance, the next stage was to establish how planning competences is related to staff performance. This was achieved by computing the Spearman correlation coefficient and coefficient of determination. The details are presented in the table below, accompanied with and analysis and interpretation.

Table 4.2.2: Correlation between planning competences and staff performance

		Planning competences	Staff performance
Planning competences	Pearson Correlation	1	.541
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.293
	N	74	74
Staff performance	Pearson Correlation	.293	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	74	74
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Primary data

According to results presented in Table 4.2.2 the Pearson correlation coefficients indicate that the relationship between planning competence and staff performance is positive and statistically significant at 99% significance level ($\rho = .541, P < 0.001$). Since the correlation does not indicate the percentage variation in the dependent variable caused by the independent variable, a coefficient of determination, which is the square of the correlation coefficient was computed. The coefficient of determination was expressed into percentage to determine the effect of planning competences on staff performance. Based on this statistic, it is revealed that planning competences accounted for 29.3% of variation in staff performance.

4.5 Regression results indicating the effect of planning competences on staff performance

Table 4.4.3: Relationship between planning competence and staff performance

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
1 (Constant) Planning competences	1.689	.215		7.873	.001
	.624	.053	.762	11.842	.001
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of estimate	
1	.762 ^a	.581	.577	.41575	

a. Predictor: (Constant), Planning competences a. Dependent variable: Performance

Source: Primary data, 2017

As can be seen in Table 4.4.3 above, linear regression model was conducted to test the first hypothesis. H1 which states that planning competence has a significant effect on performance of staff and also to determine the effect of on planning on staff performance.

The results show that planning competences which was computed to comprise simplicity, specific, realistic and completeness of plan and these were seen to have a positive significant effect on staff performance with significance level of 99% ($\beta = 0.762$, $P < 0.001$).

Planning competences further explains a 57.7% variation on the performance of staff based on the Adjusted R Square statistic. This means that H1 which states that planning competences has a significant effect on performance of staff in Muni University was supported.

5. Summary of findings

There was a moderate relationship between planning competence and staff performance. Planning competence accounted for 55.7% variation in staff performance. Linear regression results for planning competence against staff performance established that planning competence has a positive significant effect on staff performance ($\beta < 0.452$). Finding further established that planning is done in a manner that makes it simple with 83 (81%) respondents in agreement, the plans are specific with concrete and measurable objectives with 75 (73%) of the respondents in agreement, furthermore, plans have specific dates of completion with 81 (79%) in agreement, plans implemented are realistic with 85 (82%) in agreement and the plans are complete a slight majority of 53 (52%) in agreement and 25 (24%) in disagreement.

6. Discussions of the findings

The finding of the study showed that the majority 51 (49%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the plans are complete and 34 (33%) of the respondents agreed. In line with these findings, Khan (2011) in his study on the impact of planning and development on organization performance in Pakistan argued that staff need to constantly plan in order to understand new changes taking place within their learning and teaching environment. However, such planning should be simple, specific, realistic and complete.

According to Alipour (2009, 2011, 2013, 2014, 2015), planning is a substantial organization investment in getting a satisfactory return on investment thereby linking the planning functions and activities to the company's overall business activities. Thus effective planning enhances staff performance as it has been revealed in this study.

Several studies have proved that planning has a significant effect on performance (Khan, 2011, Sabir et al 2014, Odinga 2010) and thus agree with the findings in line with the first hypothesis which states that planning has a significant positive effect on staff performance in Muni University.

The finding of the study also indicated that 82 (81%) of the respondents agree that planning is done in a way that makes it simple. Organizations use a variety of methods for planning including doing SWOT analysis that provide further details and insight into the strength, weaknesses, opportunity and threats in the organization. When suitable plans are provided to the needs, demand and supply are balanced, and planning thus becomes effective. A planner should have not only skills necessary but also capacity for performance management, analysis and design and identifying planning gaps. In line with Cekada (2010), a simple plan is one that communicates its content easily and practically and it is easy to understand and act on. This is further reinforced by Judith (2002) who asserts that if plans are not simple, then their implementation may be stifled.

The finding of the study also indicated that 38 (37%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the plans implemented were specific, 37 (36%) of the respondents agreed. This is complimented by finding from the interviews where a large number of the respondents noted that specific planning has increased their chances of accomplishing tasks thus enhancing performance.

The finding of the study showed that the majority 43 (42%) of the respondents agreed that they had realistic plans and 38 (37%) of the respondents strongly agreed. These findings are supported by Liu and Batt (2005) who established a positive relationship between planning and productivity and concluded that the amount of time spent on planning leads to productivity in the organization. In this respect, the more

planning done, the more the time spent hence increased productivity in the organization.

The findings from the interviews showed that staff derived their motivation to stay in the organization longer because of good planning despite the low salary offered. These findings are supported by Masood (2013) who established that planning strongly correlates with motivation with a highly significant and more positive.

Regression results showed that planning competence has a positive significant effect on staff performance. The positive nature of the relationship meant that positive change in planning was related to change in staff performance. The positive nature of the relationship further implied that the change in planning competence was related to staff performance and vice versa. This finding are in line with the views of Picho (2011), who states that complete planning enables staff to achieve organizational goals in the shortest time possible. In earlier studies conducted by Okwir et al (2015) a moderate relationship was found between planning and staff performance with the conviction that the purpose of planning is to provide staff with task specific direction directly related to job requirements and this is directly in agreement with the finding in this study that revealed a positive relationship between planning competence and staff performance in Muni University. This study revealed that there is easy flow of communication at Muni University and this is partly because the University is still new and with few staff and as the staff are few it is easy to communicate as opposed to communication to staff in a University with many staff.

Javal (2016) who studied planning competence and performance in the Kenyan Police Force revealed that desired performance is achieve when plans are simple, specific, realistic and complete. This finding conforms to those of this study. The plans at Muni University are simple, specific, realistic and complete because of the nature of the University that is, consisting only of one faculty and one department with four programs. In this kind of situation, it is easy to avoid all the matters that make planning complex, that is many faculties, departments and programs.

7. Conclusion

From the finding of the study, it can be concluded that when planning is done in simple manner and made specific, realistic and complete, it makes planning competence very vital in an organization thus contributing significantly towards the performance of staff as explained by planning competences contributing to a variation of 57.7% in the overall performance of staff.

8. Recommendation

Muni University should make sure that planning is done in simple manner and made specific, realistic and complete in order to enhance staff performance. They should further focus on delivering these plans at the right time and involve the targeted respondents in planning and implementations of the plans so as to ensure that planning is done to enhance performance.

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